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Mother Mary an Awakened Woman of Prophetic Hope: A Call to be in Solidarity with the Wounded World

Fabian Jose, UMI

Jnana Deepa, Pune 411014

Abstract: The hope filled Blessed Virgin Mary has a special place in our Christian life. We have experienced Mother Mary's hope filled protection at various stages of our life. We are encouraged to cultivate a genuine devotion to our Blessed Mother to live a hope filled life. The author shows that in our world of darkness, confusion and hopelessness Mary is holding our hand and taking us closer to the person of Christ to intercede for the world and to live a hope filled life.

Keywords: Hope, Mother Mary, Mother of Mercy, Comfort of Migrants.

Introduction

'*Dum spiro, spero*' (while I breathe, I hope) is a well-known dictum of the ancient Romans. It has been observed that humans can live without anything except hope. The mounting number of suicides in the present context of the world restates that hope is indispensable, if we are to live as sane human beings. The Holy Father Pope Benedict XVI acknowledged during his papacy the absolute necessity of hope in today's world. This prompted him to focus his second encyclical on the

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theme of Christian hope. Hope is the kernel of Christian spirituality. The fulfilment of this virtue is concretely unfolded in our Blessed Mother. As an awakened woman of prophetic hope Mary responded to the will of God generously in total surrender.

The hope filled Blessed Virgin Mary has a special place in our Christian life. We have experienced Mother Mary's hope filled protection at various stages of our life. We are encouraged to cultivate a genuine devotion to our Blessed Mother to live a hope filled life during this pandemic COVID-19. In this present moment of uncertainty and anxiety, Holy Father Pope Francis added new 3 titles to the Marian litany: 'Comfort of Migrants,' 'Mother of Mercy,' and 'Mother of Hope.' In relation to this Marian title "Mary Mother of Hope" we shall contemplate on "**Mother Mary: an awakened woman of prophetic hope in today's wounded world.**" May our Blessed Mother enable us to live a hope filled life by placing our trust completely in the Lord as we celebrate Mary's Assumption on 15 August:

1. **Mary is the hope filled Star of the Church:** Pope Benedict in his encyclical *Spe Salvi* highlights that our life is a voyage and often it is dark and stormy, we need stars in our voyage to indicate the route. The true stars of hope in our life are certainly, Jesus Christ the true light. But to reach him we also need lights and Mary is that light which guides us along our way. She has taken this invitation as a vocation to accompany her children of the pilgrim church by giving us hope amidst challenges, sufferings and pains. Pope Francis affirms, "We Christians are not orphans, because we believe that we have a mother in heaven." Jesus while hanging on the cross has given us Mary as our Mother of Hope to the church to accompany us in our sufferings and pains. The Virgin Mary star of hope, joyfully and gracefully protects the mother church during these dark moments of pandemic COVID-19.
2. **Mary hope of the consecrated women and men:** Mary was a deep woman of prayer, faith, and hope. Amidst the trials, pains

and difficulties Mary lived her life in profound faith and hope. She gives hope to the consecrated to live the evangelical councils in a radical manner to follow Jesus. The consecrated men and women who imitate our Blessed mother who lived constantly in faith and hope, the mother who listened, the mother who responded to the impossible and the mother who lived a life of contemplation. In the year 1970, on April 24, Pope Paul VI, exhorted the faithful gathered around the statute of our lady of Bonoria in Sardenia: “If we want to be Christians we have to be Marian.” We have to recognize the essential, relationship that unites our blessed mother to Jesus and with us. She invites the consecrated to imitate her and live her spirit as she is our life, our sweetness, our hope and our way to Jesus.

3. **Mary Mother of hope to the sick and suffering amidst Covid -19:** Throughout the Church’s history, Christians have sought Mary’s intercession in times of serious illness including pestilence and plagues. As a loving mother, Mary always responds with comfort and the healing grace of her Son. Today, amidst the pandemic Covid-19, the Holy Father Pope Francis dedicated the Catholic Church to the maternal protection and intercession of our Blessed Mother. Let us look at Mary the health of the sick and the Star of the stormy Sea, to accept this troubled time with hope and trust in the Lord. Let us listen to the voices of our Blessed Mother as she speaks to us during this distressed time, to face the wind and the silence, the darkness and the rain, the sound of the ambulance sirens, the painful departure of the COVID victims, the cry of the bereaved families of the pandemic, the struggles of the health workers, in all these situations may we entrust them to God and live our life hopefully.
4. **Mary Mother of hope to the hopeless:** Christian hope never gives up, it is hope against hopelessness. The more one realises that they are unable to help oneself, the more one hopes in God’s promised help. For the hungry, the migrants, refugees, the poor and the oppressed, the situation is absolutely hopeless. The validity of the prayer of St. Paul

is indeed timeless: “May the God of hope fill you all with joy and peace in believing, so that by the power of the Holy Spirit you may abound in hope” (Rm.15/13). In the Magnificat (Lk 1: 46-55) Mary praises God. Mary’s song of trust symbolises all the materially poor, socially oppressed, differently afflicted. The threefold revolution of scattering the economically secure, morally self-righteous and spiritually pharisaic is indeed the kernel of God’s redeeming activity. Today, Mary’s maternal loving presence offers courage and hope to the vulnerable members of the society who faces hopelessness and brokenness. She reassures them that they are never alone, never without the consolation and hope won by her Son Jesus’ suffering, death and resurrection to a new life.

5. **Mary, Mother of hope to us:** Christian hope flows out of God’s love and justice. Christian salvation has always been considered a social reality. Similarly, the hope that Mary offers us that God will give us the strength to bear what may come on our way. It is assured by Jesus “See the kingdom of God is among you,” (Lk. 17:21), which is in our hearts, in our families, in our religious communities, in our congregations, in our diocese, in our ministries, in our prayer and in all our activities. The basis of our hope is that God is acting in unseen yet powerful ways as He acted in the life of Mother Mary.
6. **Mary, Mother of Hope Restores the World:** Mother Mary, as an awakened woman believed and hoped in a God who was faithful to His promises in the past, present and in the future. Today, when we look at the world it suffers from poverty, social, economic exploitation, the increasing gap between the rich and the poor, the alarming increase in terrorism and human brutality. Mary encourages us to trust in God and to hope beyond all adversities. It is only the restoration of the joy of living and the courage to hope and the ability to reconcile with oneself, with others and with God that can facilitate the

realization of the reign of God in our lives. As Pope Francis emphasized “Let us invoke Mother Mary’s intercession for all the situations in the world that are most in need of hope: hope for peace, for justice, hope for a dignified life.”

Conclusion

In our world of darkness, confusion and hopelessness Mary is holding our hand and taking us closer to the person of Christ to intercede for the world and to live a hope filled life. Let us not lose hope amidst the challenging realities of this world because we have a mother to rely on. She walks with us, supports us, and guides us, to be in solidarity with the wounded world.

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Fabian Jose, UMI, is professor of spirituality at Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology. She has specialised on Thomas Merton. Email: fabianaumi@gmail.com

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